

**GRAIN YIELD OF MUNG BEAN GROWN AS A DOUBLE
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Institute<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.21054646>**ARTICLE INFO**Received: 25th June 2026Accepted: 27th June 2026Online: 29th June 2026**KEYWORDS**

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ABSTRACT

This article presents the results of a study on the effects of planting date, seeding rate, and microbiological fertilizers on the grain yield of mung bean grown as a double crop under the takyr-like soil conditions of the Kashkadarya region. The results showed that the highest grain yield (1.72 t/ha-1) was obtained when the mung bean cultivar “Durдона” was sown on 20–25 June at a seeding rate of 14 kg/ha, with seeds treated before sowing with the microbiological fertilizer “Organit-N”. Delaying sowing until 5–10 July reduced grain yield by 0.32–0.51 t/ha-1, while increasing the seeding rate by 4–8 kg/ha resulted in a yield reduction of 0.07–0.20 t/ha-1. Pre-sowing seed treatment with “Organit-N” increased grain yield by 0.38 t/ha-1 compared with the untreated control.

Today, rapid population growth, the need to ensure food security, and the efficient use of agricultural land have made the cultivation of double crops one of the priority areas of modern agriculture. In this regard, mung bean (*Vigna radiata* L.), characterized by its short growing season, high protein content, and ability to improve soil fertility, is considered one of the most important grain legume crops. Mung bean seeds contain 22–28% crude protein, vitamins, minerals, and essential amino acids required for human nutrition, making them a valuable raw material for the food industry, livestock production, and processing industries.

In Uzbekistan, the cultivation of mung bean as a double crop after winter wheat harvesting has been expanding to ensure the efficient use of vacant agricultural land. However, obtaining high and stable grain yields under double-cropping conditions largely depends on planting date, seeding rate, soil and climatic conditions, and the applied cultivation practices. In particular, delayed sowing shortens the crop growth period, reduces photosynthetic activity, and negatively affects the formation of yield components, ultimately resulting in lower grain productivity.

Mung bean (*Vigna radiata* L.) originated in India, where it has been cultivated since ancient times. From India, its cultivation spread to China, Myanmar, Laos, and Vietnam. At present, mung bean is widely grown in India, Pakistan, China, Myanmar, Vietnam, Iraq, Afghanistan, Egypt, Syria, Ethiopia, and Sri Lanka [1].

Developing effective agronomic practices to achieve high grain yield and quality in mung bean requires optimization of cultivation factors, including planting method, planting date, seeding rate, plant density, irrigation regime, and mineral fertilizer application. Under the foothill plain conditions of the Kashkadarya region, the highest grain yield (1.93 t/ha^{-1}) was obtained when mung bean was grown as a double crop after winter wheat and sown on 1 July at a density of $400,000$ viable seeds ha^{-1} . Delayed planting and higher seeding rates were found to reduce the protein content of the grain [3, 4].

According to the recommendations of Davronov and Kholiqov [2], high grain productivity of mung bean grown as a double crop can be achieved by cultivating the "Durдона" and "Marjon" cultivars at a plant density of $300,000$ plants ha^{-1} and applying the biostimulant "Avangard Start" as a foliar spray during the growing season. This practice increased grain yield by 21.3% and 27.1%, respectively.

One of the greatest achievements of Uzbekistan's agriculture during the years of independence has been the introduction and expansion of cereal crops, particularly winter wheat, in the cropping pattern. This has significantly improved the efficiency of irrigated land use and created opportunities for cultivating various agricultural crops after winter wheat harvest. As a result, short crop rotation systems have been developed, while farmers have continuously enhanced their scientific knowledge and practical skills, enabling them to harvest two or even three crops from the same field within a single year. Currently, grain legumes such as mung bean, soybean, and common bean, along with several other crops, are widely cultivated as double crops after winter wheat in different regions of the country.

As demonstrated in the present study, planting date, seeding rate, and the application of microbiological fertilizers influenced the growth, development, biomass accumulation, and biometric characteristics of mung bean grown as a double crop after winter wheat. These effects were ultimately reflected in the grain yield of the crop.

According to the results obtained during the three-year study, the average grain yield of mung bean ranged from 0.66 to 1.72 t/ha^{-1} across the experimental treatments. The highest grain yield (1.72 t/ha^{-1}) was recorded in treatment 5, where the mung bean cultivar "Durдона" was sown at a seeding rate of 14 kg ha^{-1} during the early planting period (20–25 June), using viable seeds treated with the microbiological fertilizer "Organit-N" before sowing.

Planting date had a significant effect on grain yield. Under early sowing conditions (20–25 June), grain yield ranged from 0.98 to 1.72 t/ha^{-1} , whereas delayed sowing (5–10 July) reduced yield to 0.66 – 1.21 t/ha^{-1} . Consequently, delaying planting decreased grain yield by 0.32 – 0.51 t/ha^{-1} compared with early sowing.

Seeding rate also markedly influenced grain productivity. Under early sowing conditions, grain yield ranged from 1.18 to 1.56 t/ha^{-1} at a seeding rate of 10 kg ha^{-1} , increased to 1.25 – 1.72 t/ha^{-1} at 14 kg ha^{-1} , and ranged from 0.98 to 1.57 t/ha^{-1} at 18 kg ha^{-1} . Increasing the seeding rate from 10 to 14 kg ha^{-1} resulted in a grain yield increase of 0.07 – 0.16 t/ha^{-1} . However, a further increase to 18 kg ha^{-1} reduced grain yield by up to 0.20 t/ha^{-1} . The superior performance observed at the seeding rate of 14 kg ha^{-1} was associated with the formation of an optimum plant population, which ensured efficient utilization of available growth resources. In contrast, increasing the seeding rate to 18 kg ha^{-1} led to excessive plant density, resulting in stronger interplant competition and a reduction in the number of

productive branches, yield components per plant, and 1000-seed weight, ultimately decreasing grain yield. A similar trend was also observed under late sowing conditions.

Table

**Effects of Planting Date, Seeding Rate, and Microbiological Fertilizer Application on Grain Yield of Mung Bean:
Three-Year Mean (2018–2020)**

Sre. No.	Planting date	Seeding rate, kg ha ⁻¹	Type of microbiological fertilizer	Grain yield, t/ha ⁻¹				Yield increase compared with planting date, t/ha ⁻¹	Yield increase compared with seeding rate (t ha ⁻¹)	Yield increase compared with microbiological fertilizer treatments (t ha ⁻¹)
				2018 year	2019 year	2020 year	Three-year mean			
1-9	20-25.06	10,0	Control	11.3	11.7	12.6	11.8	+3.7		-
			“Organit-N”	14.9	15.5	16.4	15.6	+4.5		+3.8
			“Organit-P”	13.8	14.4	15.3	14.5	+4.3		+2.7
		14,0	Control	11.9	12.1	13.5	12.5	+3.5	+0.7/+2.7	-
			“Organit-N”	16.7	16.7	18.1	17.2	+5.1	+1.6/+1.5	+4.7
			“Organit-P”	15.5	15.5	16.9	16.0	+4.8	+1.5/+1.5	+3.5
		18,0	Control	9.0	9.6	11.0	9.8	+3.2		-
			“Organit-N”	14.9	15.2	16.9	15.7	+5.5		+5.9
			“Organit-P”	13.8	14.1	15.8	14.5	+5.3		+4.7
10-18	05-10.07	10,0	Control	7.6	7.9	8.9	8.1			-
			“Organit-N”	10.2	11.0	12.0	11.1			+3.0
			“Organit-P”	9.4	10.0	11.1	10.2			+2.1
		14,0	Control	8.4	8.8	9.8	9.0		+0.9/+2.4	-
			“Organit-N”	11.2	11.7	13.3	12.1		+1.0/+1.9	+3.1
			“Organit-P”	10.4	10.9	12.4	11.2		+1.0/+2.0	+2.2
		18,0	Control	6.0	6.5	7.4	6.6			-
			“Organit-N”	9.4	10.0	11.3	10.2			+3.6
			“Organit-P”	8.5	8.9	10.1	9.2			+2.6

In addition to planting date and seeding rate, pre-sowing seed treatment with microbiological fertilizers had a significant effect on mung bean grain yield. The application of microbiological fertilizers consistently enhanced grain productivity. Under early sowing conditions (20–25 June) at a seeding rate of 10 kg ha⁻¹, pre-sowing seed treatment with different microbiological fertilizers resulted in grain yields ranging from 1.45 to 1.56 t/ha⁻¹, which was 0.27–0.38 t/ha⁻¹ higher than that of the untreated control. Moreover, seed treatment with “Organit-N” produced an additional 0.11 t/ha⁻¹ of grain yield compared with “Organit-P”. The same trend was consistently observed across all seeding rates (Table).

Conclusion. The results of the present study indicate that under the takyr-like soil conditions of the Kashkadarya region. the highest grain yield of mung bean grown as a double crop can be achieved by sowing viable seeds during the early planting period (20–25 June) at a seeding rate of 14 kg ha⁻¹. followed by pre-sowing seed treatment with the microbiological fertilizer “Organit-N”. This cultivation practice increased grain yield by 0.51 t/ha⁻¹ compared with late sowing. by 0.15–0.16 t/ha⁻¹ compared with other seeding rates. and by 0.47 t/ha⁻¹ compared with the untreated control. Therefore. the combined optimization of planting date. seeding rate. and pre-sowing seed inoculation with “Organit-N” is recommended as an effective agronomic practice for maximizing mung bean grain yield under double-cropping conditions.

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